

Growth Performance and Feed Utilization of *Clarias gariepinus* Juveniles (African Catfish) Fed Rabbit Droppings Supplemented Feed

Uwaeziozi U. C^{1*}., Ayegba E. O²., Okani-Onyejiaka M. C¹.

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Science Umuagwo Imo State.

²Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Science Umuagwo Imo State

*Corresponding author: uche19822000@gmail.com

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Abstract: This study evaluated the growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* juveniles fed diets supplemented with sun-dried rabbit droppings and Black Soldier Fly (BSF) larvae. A total of 400 four-week-old juveniles were randomly assigned to four dietary treatments in a completely randomized design (CRD), with 100 fish per treatment and four replicates per group. The trial lasted 90 days. The dietary treatments included: Group A (100% conventional feed), Group B (100% BSF larvae meal), Group C (10% rabbit droppings + 90% BSF), and Group D (10% rabbit droppings + 90% conventional feed). Rabbit droppings were sun-dried, milled, and incorporated into the feed mixtures of Groups C and D. Dehydrated and pelletized BSF larvae were sourced from a commercial supplier, while conventional fish feed was store-bought. Growth parameters including weight gain (WG), specific growth rate (SGR), and feed conversion ratio (FCR) were assessed biweekly. Results revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in growth performance among treatments. Group D exhibited the highest mean weight gain (1767 g), significantly surpassing Groups B and C, and was statistically comparable to Group A. No significant differences were observed in FCR or hepatosomatic index (HSI) among the groups, indicating that liver health and feed efficiency were not adversely affected by the inclusion of rabbit droppings or BSF larvae. The findings demonstrate that partial substitution of conventional feed and BSF pellets with rabbit droppings can serve as a sustainable and cost-effective alternative feed source in catfish aquaculture without compromising fish health or performance.

Keywords: *Clarias gariepinus*, rabbit droppings, Black Soldier Fly, aquaculture, alternative protein

Introduction

The escalating cost and limited availability of conventional feed ingredients such as soybean meal and fishmeal pose significant challenges to sustainable aquaculture, particularly in the production of *Clarias gariepinus* (African catfish). These conventional protein sources are not only essential in livestock nutrition but also critical for human consumption, raising economic and ethical concerns about their long-term use in animal feeds (Ondiba et al., 2022). With the rising global demand for animal protein, aquaculture systems are under pressure to adopt cost-effective and sustainable feeding strategies (FAO, 2020).

In this context, the exploration of non-conventional feed resources has gained traction. Among them, recycled animal waste specifically rabbit droppings offers a promising alternative due to its favorable nutrient profile, including relatively high nitrogen content, microbial richness, and the presence of macro- and micronutrients (Ano & Ekefan, 2023; Monebi & Ugwumba, 2014). Research has demonstrated that rabbit manure can be used either to enhance pond fertility or as a direct component in feed formulations without adverse effects on fish growth (Tabaro et al., 2021; Adjanke et

al., 2023). Proximate analyses indicate that rabbit droppings contain appreciable levels of crude protein (15–20%), fiber (15–25%), and essential elements such as phosphorus, calcium, and potassium (Ajayi et al., 2024;), making them suitable for low-cost feeding systems in aquaculture.

Simultaneously, the black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae (BSFL) have emerged as a viable insect-based protein source due to their ability to bioconvert organic waste including animal manure into a high-protein, lipid-rich biomass suitable for animal and aquaculture feed (Hua, 2021; Brun et al., 2020; He et al., 2022; Naruti et al., 2021). BSFL meal has been shown to improve growth performance, feed utilization, and gut health in fish (Limbu et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2022), while also contributing to reduced environmental pollution and greenhouse gas emissions through waste valorization.

Combining BSF larvae with rabbit droppings in fish feed formulation may offer a synergistic and sustainable solution to the current feed crisis. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* juveniles fed diets supplemented with rabbit droppings and BSFL meal, as a strategy to reduce

dependency on conventional feed inputs while promoting environmental and economic sustainability in aquaculture.

Materials and Method

Preliminary Analysis

Prior to the initiation of the feeding trial, rabbit droppings were collected, sun-dried, and subjected to proximate analysis as well as selected mineral and vitamin profiling (**Table 1**) to evaluate their nutritional suitability as a dietary component for aquaculture feed formulations.

Experimental Site and Animal Management

The study was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria. A total of 400 juvenile *Clarias gariepinus* (African catfish), which were bought at four weeks post-fingerling stage from a commercial fish farm in Owerri Imo state, were used for this experiment. The fish underwent a two-week acclimatization period, all 400 juveniles were housed in a 1000-liter capacity tarpaulin pond, during which they were fed exclusively with conventional commercial feed.

Following acclimation, fish were randomly distributed into four dietary treatment groups, with four replicates of 25 fish each per group, the replicates were put each in 200-liter capacity tarpaulin pond. Simultaneously, ten (10) adult rabbits were housed under an intensive system in an automated hutch equipped with wire-mesh flooring designed to prevent contamination of feces by urine or water. Fresh droppings were collected randomly and stored under hygienic, dry conditions for subsequent use. The study lasted for 90 days.

Experimental Design and Diet Formulation

A completely randomized design (CRD) was adopted with the following treatment groups:

- **Group A:** 100% commercial (conventional) feed
- **Group B:** 100% Black Soldier Fly (BSF) larvae meal
- **Group C:** 10% rabbit droppings + 90% BSF larvae meal
- **Group D:** 10% rabbit droppings + 90% conventional feed

Commercial floating feed pellets were procured from a certified supplier, while dehydrated BSF larvae (pelletized) were obtained from Agmart Foods and Farms Ltd., Owerri, Nigeria. The rabbit droppings were

thoroughly sun-dried, milled, and incorporated into formulated feed mixtures according to treatment specifications for Groups C and D, to obtain this specification easily, for every 90kg of BSF dried larvae or conventional feed, 10kg of dried rabbit dropping was mixed in it. All feeds were pelletized to uniform size to ensure homogenous intake and reduce feed loss. Proximate compositions of nutrients in Rabbit dropping and dried black soldier fly were analyzed chemically according to the official methods of analysis described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemist (A.O.A.C.,1998).

Feeding and Husbandry Practices

Fish were fed ad libitum, three times daily at four-hour intervals. Feeding was monitored to prevent waste and ensure uniform growth. Rearing was conducted in indoor tarpaulin tanks under controlled environmental conditions.

- Water temperature was measured daily using an infrared thermometer and maintained within the range of 29 30°C.
- pH levels were checked with a digital pH meter and maintained between 6.8 and 7.3.

- Water exchange was carried out regularly by partial draining and refilling with fresh, clean water.
- Pond desilting was conducted once weekly to remove accumulated feed residue and organic debris, thereby ensuring optimal water quality.

Sampling and Data Collection

Fish sampling was performed fortnightly to monitor growth parameters. The following growth parameters were ascertained:

1. ***Weight Gain (WG)***: 30 fishes randomly picked per treatment were weighed at the inception (Initial body weight) and at the end of the experiment (final body weight) using a digital scale, they were scooped out and placed in bowl, the weight of the bowl was deducted from the total weight to get the weight of the fish. And the following formula was used in calculating weight gain:

$$\text{Weight Gain (WG)} = \text{Final Body Weight (FBW)} - \text{Initial Body Weight (IBW)}$$

2. ***Specific Growth rate (SGR)***: Specific Growth Rate (SGR) is the percentage increase in body weight

per day, showing how fast the fish is growing over a given time period.

$$SGR \quad (\%/day) \quad = \quad (ln \quad (Final \quad Body \quad Weight) - ln(Initial \quad Body \quad Weight)) \quad / \quad Number \quad of \quad days \quad \times 100$$

- ln = natural logarithm
- Final Body Weight (FBW) = average final weight of fish (g)
- Initial Body Weight (IBW) = average starting weight of fish (g)
- Number of Days = duration of the feeding trial

3. **Feed conversion ratio (FCR):** Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) measures how efficiently fish convert feed into body weight. A lower FCR means better feed efficiency.

$$FCR = Total \quad Feed \quad Intake \quad (g) \quad / \quad Total \quad weight \quad gain \quad (g)$$

- Total Feed Intake: Total amount of feed consumed per group (grams or kg)
- Total Weight Gain: Difference between final and initial body weights (g)

4. **Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER):** Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER) measures how efficiently the protein in feed contributes to body weight gain in fish.

$$PER = Total \quad Weight \quad Gain \quad (g) \quad / \quad Total \quad Protein \quad Intake \quad (g).$$

Total protein was

calculated from the crude protein quantity in total feed intake per treatment.

5. **Hepatosomatic Index (HSI):** $HSI = \{Liver \quad weight \quad (g) / Total \quad body \quad weight \quad (g)\} \times 100$

10 fishes per treatment were randomly selected and euthanized humanely by slightly tapping their head with a scalpel, the fishes were weighed using a digital balance to obtain the Total body weight, each fish was then placed dorsal side up on a clean dissection board, the mid ventral incision was made from the anal opening towards the pectoral girdle using a scalpel to gently expose the abdominal cavity and its organs. The liver was located near the stomach and removed. The liver was blotted with a tissue and weighed, this process was repeated for each of the 10 fishes randomly selected in each group and the average weight of the liver per group was deduced and recorded in grams. The liver values were plugged into the formula to calculate the HIS.

Data were recorded systematically. All procedures were carried out in

accordance with ethical standards for animal handling and aquaculture research.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected from the experiment was analysed in IBM SPSS statistical software (2019), using a one way ANOVA (Analysis

of Variance) where the result of the ANOVA was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Post hoc test for multiple comparisons was performed to compare means of all groups.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Proximate Composition of Feed Materials Used

Nutrients	Rabbit dropping	Black soldier fly larvae (dried)	Conventional fish feed
Crude Protein (%)	22	55	45
Crude Fat (%)	1.5	6.5	8
Crude Fiber (%)	20	5.0	4.5
MEkcal/kg	1.8	2.2	3.3
Sodium (%)	0.049	0.1	0.3
Calcium (%)	0.016	1.8	1.5
Phosphorous (%)	0.080	0.9	1.1

Table 2 Calculated Analysis of Experimental Feed

Nutrient Composition	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D
	100% conventional feed	100%BSFL meal	10%rabbit dropping +90% BSFL meal	10%rabbit dropping + 90% conventional feed
Crude Protein (%)	45	55	52	42
Crude Fat (%)	8	6.5	6.0	7.2
Crude Fiber (%)	4.5	5.0	6.5	6.3
MEkcal/kg	3.3	2.2	2.1	3.0
Sodium (%)	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.3
Calcium (%)	1.5	1.8	1.6	1.4

Table 3 Growth rate of African Cat fish (*Clarias Gariepinus*) supplemented with rabbit dropping

PARAMETERS	Treatment Groups				SEM
	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	
	100% conventional feed	100%BSFL meal	10%rabbit dropping +90% BSFL meal	10%rabbit dropping + 90% conventional feed	
WG (g)	1716 ^a	1596 ^b	1660 ^c	1767 ^{ab}	23.6
SGR (%)	8.27 ^{ab}	8.19 ^a	8.23 ^a	9.00 ^b	0.035
FCR	1.3 ^a	1.5 ^b	1.4 ^c	1.3 ^a	0.033
PER	31.7 ^b	26.0 ^a	31.9 ^b	38.9 ^{ab}	1.618
HIS (%)	1.68 ^a	1.60 ^b	1.65 ^c	1.70 ^a	0.014

abc, means with different superscript on the same row differ significantly (p<0.05), SEM: standard error of mean; WG- Weight gain, SGR- Specific Growth Rate, FCR- Feed Conversion Ratio, PER- Protein Efficiency Ratio, HSI- Hepatosomatic Index

	WG	SGR	FCR	PER	HIS	
WG	1	.747*	-.903**	.941**	.924**	
SGR	.747*	1	-0.508	.791*	.854**	
FCR	-.903**	-0.508	1	-.785*	-.797*	
PER	.941**	.791*	-.785*	1	.949**	
HIS	.924**	.854**	-.797*	.949**	1	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Figure 1 Correlation matrix of growth rate indices of African cat fish (*clarias gariepinus*) supplemented with rabbit dropping

The growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* juveniles across different dietary treatments observed in this study can be attributed to the distinct nutrient profiles of the experimental feed (Table 1) components

rabbit droppings, Black Soldier Fly (BSF) larvae meal, and conventional fish feed. The high crude protein content of BSF larvae (55%) likely contributed significantly to the growth observed in Groups B and C. Protein

is critical in fish diets for tissue development and energy metabolism, and its adequacy is directly correlated with improved specific growth rate (SGR) and protein efficiency ratio (PER) (Hua et al., 2021; Limbu et al., 2022). Although Group B received 100% BSF and recorded a slightly lower weight gain compared to other groups, the result suggests that while BSF is protein-rich, its balance of other nutrients (particularly energy and minerals) may not be optimal for sole use. Conversely, rabbit droppings had a modest crude protein level (22%) and high crude fiber (20%), which, in large quantities, may compromise nutrient digestibility and energy availability (Ajayi et al., 2024). However, when included at a 10% level (Groups C and D), the rabbit droppings did not negatively impact feed conversion ratio (FCR) or hepatosomatic index (HSI), and instead served as a sustainable and cost-effective feed supplement. These findings align with Tabaro et al. (2021) and Adjanke et al. (2023), who demonstrated that rabbit droppings, when properly processed and included at low levels, enhance pond productivity and contribute non-deleteriously to fish growth.

Energy-wise, conventional feed presented the highest metabolizable energy (ME = 3.3

kcal/kg), followed by BSF larvae (2.2 kcal/kg), and rabbit droppings (1.8 kcal/kg). The balanced energy-protein ratio in Group D (90% conventional feed + 10% rabbit droppings) may explain the highest weight gain (1767 g) and efficient feed utilization, as previously supported by Monebi & Ugwumba (2014), who highlighted the importance of maintaining optimal dietary energy to protein balance in aquaculture. Furthermore, the BSF meal and conventional feed were richer in essential minerals such as calcium and phosphorus, unlike rabbit droppings which showed relatively low values. Despite this, the non-significant differences in HSI across all groups imply that liver health and physiological function were not adversely affected by dietary treatments. Similar observations were made by Almeida et al. (2006) in tilapia studies evaluating liver histology in response to varied diets. Collectively, this study demonstrates that partial replacement of conventional feed with rabbit droppings and/or BSF larvae meal offers a promising pathway for sustainable aquafeed development. It supports previous reports suggesting that integrated waste-to-feed systems can effectively reduce reliance on conventional protein sources without compromising fish

health or performance (Brun et al., 2020; He et al., 2022). Understanding key performance metrics is essential when evaluating dietary impact on aquaculture species such as *Clarias gariepinus*. Growth performance parameters (Table 2) such as weight gain (WG) and specific growth rate (SGR) are critical indicators of the overall health and efficiency of nutrient utilization in fish (Sandra et al., (2024),). Feed conversion ratio (FCR) reflects how effectively feed is converted into biomass, while protein efficiency ratio (PER) evaluates how well the dietary protein supports growth (Lumbu et al., 2024). The hepatosomatic index (HSI), representing the ratio of liver weight to body weight, is an indirect marker of metabolic activity and liver health (Almeida L.C. 2006). Monitoring these parameters provides insights into the physiological response of fish to various feed formulations and helps determine the sustainability and efficacy of alternative dietary inputs.

This study assessed the growth performance and feed utilization of *Clarias gariepinus* juveniles fed varying dietary compositions that included rabbit droppings and Black Soldier Fly Larvae (BSFL) meal. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

were observed among treatment groups across multiple growth and efficiency parameters. Group D, which received 10% rabbit droppings combined with 90% conventional feed, achieved the highest mean weight gain (1767 g), significantly outperforming Groups B and C, though statistically similar to Group A. This supports the notion that incorporating a small proportion of rabbit droppings into conventional feed enhances nutrient utilization, likely due to the nitrogen-rich and microbial composition of rabbit manure (Monebi & Ugwumba, 2014). The highest SGR (9.00%) was recorded in Group D, reflecting superior growth velocity compared to other treatments. This result aligns with the findings of Brun et al. (2020) who reported that partial inclusion of animal manure enhances nutrient uptake and supports optimal growth in catfish due to improved gut microbial activity and pond fertility. Groups A and D recorded the lowest FCR values (1.3), indicating higher feed efficiency. In contrast, the FCR for Group B (100% BSFL) was significantly higher (1.5), suggesting suboptimal nutrient conversion. These findings correspond with Maina, (2021), who observed that while BSFL is a promising protein source, its amino acid profile may require

supplementation to achieve efficiency comparable to fishmeal-based diets.

Group D also demonstrated the highest PER (38.9), reflecting improved protein utilization. This was followed by Groups C and A, while Group B exhibited the lowest PER (26.0). The trend indicates that rabbit droppings, when properly dried and incorporated with either BSFL or conventional feed, enhance protein retention and growth. This aligns with the study by Limbu *et al.* (2022), which highlighted the potential of combining organic residues with insect protein to optimize feed efficiency. HSI values ranged from 1.60% to 1.70%, with no significant differences among treatments, indicating that liver health was not compromised by the inclusion of rabbit droppings or BSFL. This result corroborates with Xiaogu *et al.* (2023) in a study that show that major culprits for Liver disease in most fishes are centered on high energy diets and nutritional deficiency and diets incorporating plant residues. Correlation analysis (figure 1) was conducted to evaluate the interrelationship between critical growth and nutrient utilization parameters in *Clarias gariepinus* fed experimental diets incorporating Black Soldier Fly Larvae (BSFL) and rabbit

droppings. The matrix revealed statistically significant correlations that reinforce the biological synergy among diet quality, metabolic efficiency, and growth performance. WG was positively and significantly correlated with Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER, $r = 0.941$, $p < 0.01$), Hepatosomatic Index (HSI, $r = 0.924$, $p < 0.01$), and Specific Growth Rate (SGR, $r = 0.747$, $p < 0.05$), while it was negatively correlated with Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR, $r = -0.903$, $p < 0.01$). These findings suggest that higher weight gain is strongly associated with improved protein utilization and liver metabolic activity, and inversely related to feed input required per unit gain. This is consistent with studies by Shengyong *et al.* (2022) and Sandra *et al.* (2024), who highlighted the role of high-quality dietary protein and efficient feed utilization in enhancing fish growth. SGR exhibited strong positive correlations with PER ($r = 0.791$, $p < 0.05$) and HSI ($r = 0.854$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that rapid growth is facilitated by effective protein conversion and robust hepatic function. These results support findings by Sandra *et al.*, (2024), who emphasized the role of balanced diets in achieving optimal growth rates in catfish. FCR was negatively correlated with all other parameters, most notably with WG ($r = -$

0.903, $p < 0.01$), PER ($r = -0.785$, $p < 0.05$), and HSI ($r = -0.797$, $p < 0.05$), confirming its utility as an inverse indicator of dietary efficiency. The relatively poor FCR recorded in the 100% BSFL group (Group B) supports previous reports that BSFL protein alone may not meet all nutritional needs without supplementation (Shengyong *et al.*, 2022). PER maintained very strong positive correlations with WG, SGR, and HSI, further establishing its central role in mediating efficient growth. The positive relationship with HSI ($r = 0.949$, $p < 0.01$) is particularly significant, suggesting that improved protein conversion is supported by increased liver activity likely reflecting higher metabolic processing of nutrients. HSI also demonstrated strong, positive, and statistically significant relationships with WG, SGR, and PER, reinforcing its use as a biomarker for fish health and nutrient assimilation (Almeida *et al.*, 2006). The lack of negative implications on HSI from rabbit droppings or BSFL inclusion confirms the physiological safety of these alternative ingredients.

Conclusion

The nutrient profiles validate the experimental design: Rabbit droppings, despite lower nutrient density, serve as a

sustainable supplement. BSF larvae offer high protein, good fat, and essential minerals, making them a superior base ingredient. When combined at optimal ratios (e.g., 10% rabbit + 90% BSF or conventional), the diets promote growth comparable to full conventional feed, with reduced cost and environmental impact.

The inclusion of 10% rabbit droppings in catfish diets particularly when combined with conventional feed significantly enhanced growth performance, feed efficiency, and protein utilization, without adverse effects on liver health. Although 100% BSFL diets supported moderate growth, their performance was comparatively lower, indicating the need for formulation adjustments. These findings contribute to the body of knowledge supporting sustainable aqua feed innovations using alternative protein sources.

The correlation matrix offers strong evidence that diets incorporating BSFL, particularly when combined with rabbit droppings, enhance fish growth via improved protein efficiency and feed utilization. While 100% BSFL diets may exhibit limitations in FCR, their strategic use in mixed formulations presents a

sustainable and effective alternative to conventional feeds.

Recommendations for Further Studies

Nutritional Optimization of BSFL Diets

Since 100% BSFL diets showed relatively poorer FCR and PER, future studies should focus on amino acid balancing, fat reduction, or enzymatic pre-treatment to improve digestibility and protein bioavailability.

Dose-Response Studies on Rabbit Dropping Inclusion

Investigate the optimal percentage of rabbit droppings in fish diets beyond the 10% used while assessing safety, nutrient contribution, and possible accumulation of undesirable microbes or metabolites.

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